

Impact Testing of Fibre-Reinforced Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

Techniques for determining the mechanical properties of composite materials under tensile impact loading are briefly reviewed and the difficulties encountered are discussed. A new method, based on the standard tensile version of the split Hopkinson's pressure bar (SHPB) apparatus, is described and the validity of data obtained by this means is established. Dynamic stress-strain curves for unidirectionally reinforced CFRP are presented and compared with those determined at lower rates. The limitations of the testing technique are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The need for a full characterisation of the behaviour of fibre reinforced composites under dynamic loading conditions has prompted numerous investigations in recent years (1,2). Nevertheless, because of the experimental difficulties involved few reliable data are available. Much of the work that has been done has employed the instrumented Charpy test in which a notched beam specimen is subjected to impact bending (3). Although load-time records obtained from the instrumented tup may be used to estimate the energy absorbed in the various stages of the fracturing process, stress wave reflections and the complex geometry of the specimen inhibit any fundamental analysis of the material response and its dependence on loading rate (4). A need for the development of tests covering a wide range of loading rates, up to impact, in uniaxial tension and compression and in pure shear has been clear for some time (5) and has recently been restated (4). For isotropic materials, tests at the highest rates of loading are frequently performed using the SHPB technique. In recent years this technique has been adapted to the testing of composite materials in compression (6) and torsion (7) while a high-speed punch version of the SHPB has been used (8) to determine the resistance to dynamic perforation. The greatest difficulty has been experienced, however, in obtaining reliable data for impact tension. Tensile strain rates of about 10/s have been obtained in an apparatus using a gas-driven piston (9) while rates approaching 500/s were achieved when an explosive charge was used to drive the impacting head (1). In both cases high-speed photographic techniques were required to monitor strain and in the latter investigation slipping at the clamps was a major problem. Drop-weight techniques have been used by several investigators (10), strain being determined from strain gauges attached directly

to the specimen. This method of strain measurement is very accurate up to the point at which the gauges fail but is unsatisfactory for materials which exhibit surface damage prior to fracture. It is also clear that the drop-weight technique, as developed in these investigations, is not free of stress wave reflections in the load cell (2). These are superimposed on the specimen stress-time response.

The only previous application of the SHPB technique to impact tension testing of composites is in the work of Kawata et al. (11). In their machine, which works on the bar-block principle, a cylindrical tensile specimen with a screw fixing is used. Accurately coaxial impact is required on the impact block to minimise bending stresses in the specimen. Very recently, however, another tensile impact test using the SHPB technique has been successfully developed at Oxford. Specimen design closely follows the proposals of Ewins (12), which have gained widespread acceptance for the quasi-static tension testing of carbon/epoxy composites (13). The testing technique is similar to that used for isotropic materials (14) but incorporates an instrumented loading, or input, bar. Stress equilibrium across the specimen is achieved early in the test and good agreement is obtained between the measurements of elastic strain determined from strain gauges mounted on the specimen and those determined from the Hopkinson bar analysis. The present communication describes the development and validation of this technique and its application to the tensile impact testing of uniaxially reinforced carbon/epoxy composite. The behaviour observed is compared with that found in tests performed at lower rates.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

In the original compression version of the SHPB the specimen is sandwiched between two elastic loading bars and the incident, reflected and transmitted stress waves are determined from strain gauges attached to these loading bars on either side of the specimen. In the standard tensile version of the apparatus the input loading bar becomes the weighbar tube within which the output, or inertia, bar slides freely, the specimen connecting the two at the yoke. In a specimen test strain gauges on the inertia bar monitor the transmitted stress wave. To determine the input conditions, however, a separate 'elastic' test is required, performed under identical impact conditions but with the specimen and inertia bar replaced by an elastic bar. For tests on ductile metal specimens this enables the dynamic plastic strain and strain rate to be determined with reasonable accuracy using specimens of a gauge length short enough for the attainment of stress equilibrium across the specimen to be assumed from an early stage in the test. This technique does not, however, allow for an accurate determination of strain during elastic deformation of the specimen.

When applied to composite materials several major problems arise. Because of the difficulty of ensuring a tensile failure in the gauge section rather than a shear failure in the grips and because of the need to minimise stress concentrations associated with the anisotropic nature of the material, significantly longer test specimens are required, making the attainment of stress equilibrium across the specimen more difficult. In addition, since for most composite materials the total strain to failure is only a small fraction of that obtained in metal specimens, the accurate determination of strain becomes very much more critical. For these reasons the standard tensile version of the SHPB was modified, see fig. 1, to include an instrumented input bar preceding the specimen and inertia bar and also sliding freely within the weighbar tube. Strain gauges at two stations on the input bar allow the incident and reflected waves to be monitored in the specimen test itself. Thus the validity of the assumption of stress equilibrium across the specimen may be directly checked and strain determination in the specimen may be made from measurements taken in a single test, eliminating the need to compare results from two potentially slightly different tests.

Within the constraints of the existing weighbar tube, however, the introduction of the input bar limits the maximum length of the inertia bar and hence the maximum duration of

test for which the full dynamic analysis is possible. As is apparent from fig. 1, which shows the Lagrange diagram for the modified tensile SHPB, the time interval over which the wave analysis in the input bar can be carried out cannot conveniently exceed $(T_2 - T_1)$. Since in the present apparatus $T_2 \approx 55 \mu\text{s}$ and $T_1 \approx 25 \mu\text{s}$ it is necessary that the specimen should fracture within about $30 \mu\text{s}$. In practice this limits the application of the technique to uniaxially reinforced CFRP and initial results will be presented for specimens of this material.

SPECIMEN DETAILS

Unidirectionally-reinforced carbon/epoxy specimens having the dimensions shown in fig. 2 were cut with the tensile axis parallel to the direction of reinforcement from 2mm plate supplied by Bristol Composite Materials Ltd. The fibres were of type HYFIL-Torayca-130-S in a proprietary resin system of type R7H, a modified bisphenol A medium temperature epoxy similar to Araldite MY750. A typical quasi-static tensile strength of 1.2GPa and tensile modulus of 131GPa were quoted by the manufacturer for a composite volume fraction of 60%. The parallel grip regions of the specimen were fixed into parallel-sided slots in the loading bars using Chemlok 304 high-strength epoxy adhesive. With a grip region of length 19mm tensile failure was obtained in the specimen gauge region before shear failure occurred in the adhesive. Because of the relatively long grip section it was anticipated that problems might arise from stress wave reflections at the sections AA and BB in fig. 1. In practice, however, the change in impedance across these sections was so slight that any reflections resulting were too small to be detected.

As an additional check on the Hopkinson bar analysis for strain and strain rate, some tests were performed with a further set of strain gauges attached directly to the gauge section of the specimen. Techni Measure 120 Ω strain gauges, type FL3A, having an active gauge region 3mm long by 1.9mm wide, were bonded centrally on each face of the parallel central region of the specimen using the recommended cyanoacrylate adhesive.

VALIDATION OF IMPACT TESTING TECHNIQUE

A typical set of strain-time traces for a test in which additional calibration gauges were attached directly to the specimen is shown in fig. 3a. The small perturbation, which is regularly observed in such tests near the start of the transmitted strain-time trace, ϵ_{III} coincides in time with the breakdown of the specimen gauges, ϵ_S , shortly before the specimen fractures. It is thought to be due to some resulting electrical interference. In tests where no gauges are attached directly to the specimen, see fig. 3b, no such perturbation is observed. From the Lagrange diagram of fig. 1 it may be seen that, in the absence of dispersion and for times $\ll T_1$ identical signals should be recorded at stations I and II. This is confirmed in fig. 3b where it is shown that these two signals may be superimposed almost exactly for times up to about $25 \mu\text{s}$. Standard strain gauge bridges and two dual-channel transient recorders were used to store the strain-time traces of fig. 3. These were then subsequently displayed and photographed on an oscilloscope screen while for calculation purposes a hard copy could be produced on a chart recorder.

Data obtained in this way was used in the Hopkinson bar analysis illustrated in fig. 4 for a test on a CFRP specimen impacted at a velocity of about 10m/s. Again the strain-time traces from the two sets of input bar gauges are seen to superimpose almost exactly for times up to about $25 \mu\text{s}$. The subsequent difference between these two traces is used to determine the velocity and stress at the input end of the specimen, section CC in fig. 1. The corresponding stress and velocity trace for the output end of the specimen, section DD in fig. 1, derived from the inertia bar gauges, is delayed by just over $2 \mu\text{s}$, the time for an elastic wave to travel between sections CC and DD in a CFRP specimen. The stress-time traces for the two ends of the specimen, σ_{CC} and ϵ_{III} are seen to coincide very closely almost from the start of loading, confirming the validity of the assumption of stress equilibrium across the specimen.

The corresponding strain is obtained by integrating between the velocity time curves

for the two ends of the specimen in the usual way, giving the stress-strain curve of fig. 5a. The specimen fails after about 25 μ s at a stress of 1.27GPa and a strain, related to the gauge length of 19mm, i.e. from CC to DD in fig. 1, of about 0.9%. The average strain rate was about 350/s. The stress-strain curve shows an initial linear region, corresponding to a modulus of 142GPa, followed by a slight increase in stiffness preceding failure. Also shown, in fig. 5b, is the stress-strain curve for the same test but with strain measurements obtained from the gauges attached directly to the specimen and relating, therefore, to the deformation in the parallel central section of the specimen, i.e. for a gauge length of 3mm. The two curves are very closely similar. At all stress levels the specimen strain gauges indicate a marginally lower strain than that derived from the Hopkinson bar analysis giving, therefore, a slightly higher initial modulus, 144GPa compared with 142GPa. As might be expected, the specimen gauges break down slightly before the failure of the specimen, i.e. at 23 μ s and at a strain of 0.86% giving an average strain rate of about 370/s.

CONSIDERATIONS OF EXPERIMENTAL ACCURACY

The close correlation between the two experimental curves of fig. 5 encourages considerable confidence in the validity of the testing technique. Both curves, however, rely on the same stress-time data and on the same assumption of stress equilibrium across the specimen. The accuracy of stress measurement at the inertia bar gauges is estimated to be about $\pm 2\%$, after making some allowance for dispersion and wave reflections in the grip section, DD to BB. The accuracy of stress measurement on the input side is probably less good because of the need to take the difference between two transient signals after adjusting for the time difference between them. The validity of the check on stress equilibrium depends both on the accuracy of stress measurement and also on the ability to identify with confidence the time zero's of the various transient signals. This confidence is strengthened by the use of transient recorders with a time resolution of 0.1 μ s which allows an accurate correlation to be made between the actual wave transit times between the various gauge stations and those predicted by elementary elastic wave theory. Since the specimen shows an essentially linear elastic behaviour this correlation may be carried through between gauge stations II and III. Allowance for a modified elastic wave speed in the grip regions, AA to CC and DD to BB, reduces the overall transit times by about 1.4 μ s. An error in time measurement of this order corresponds to an error of about $\pm 3\%$ in the strain determined by the Hopkinson bar analysis. The stress-time signals for the two ends of the specimen may also be displaced relative to each other, affecting the validity of the assumed stress equilibrium and modifying slightly the average stress in the specimen at any given time. Taking all these effects together the maximum error in the modulus as determined by the Hopkinson bar analysis is estimated at ± 7 GPa, i.e. about $\pm 5\%$. A similar accuracy would be expected for the results based on strain measurements made from the specimen gauges.

As noted above, the introduction of the instrumented input bar limits the maximum duration of test for which the full dynamic analysis is possible so that complete stress-strain curves may only be obtained for specimens fracturing within $\sim 30 \mu$ s. As will be reported elsewhere, however, it has proved possible, using tests on CFRP specimens, to calibrate for the elastic input conditions in the earlier version of impact tester (14). This technique has been used in preliminary tests to failure on GFRP specimens, where times to fracture may reach $\sim 100 \mu$ s.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to determine the effect of strain rate on the tensile deformation and failure of CFRP, tests were performed on the same design of specimen in an Instron loading machine at a rate of $\sim 10^{-4}$ /s, in a hydraulically operated loading machine (15) at a rate of ~ 10 /s and in the original version of impact tester at a rate of ~ 450 /s using the technique described above. The stress-strain curves obtained are presented in Fig. 6. The solid line and the quoted values of strain rate and modulus were derived in each case

from tests in which strain gauges were attached directly to the specimen. The scatter bands refer to data from further tests without strain gauges on the specimen. Over nearly 7 orders of magnitude no effect of strain rate could be detected on either the tensile modulus, 146 ± 6 GPa, or the stress at fracture, 1.2 ± 0.1 GPa. A similar fracture mode, i.e. a tensile failure in the centre of the parallel gauge region with little damage to either side of the fracture surface, was observed at all 3 rates.

As far as is known no other directly comparable data are available. Similar tests, but on carbon/epoxy specimens with a plain-woven cloth reinforcement, were performed by Kawata et al. (11) who also found the mechanical response to be relatively insensitive to strain rate. Griffiths and Martin, however, in tests on unidirectionally-reinforced carbon/epoxy specimens in the compression SHPB (6) found a bilinear stress-strain curve and a significant increase in the initial modulus with strain rate. The bilinear response they suggested might be due to specimen geometry, since an increase in the length of their cylindrical compression specimens led to a disappearance of the effect. Although the dynamic modulus, 180GPa, determined in the SHPB, was quoted to an accuracy of $\pm 7\%$, it is compared to an alternative dynamic modulus of 123GPa determined by an ultrasonic pulse technique and a static modulus of 105GPa. Some question must remain, therefore, regarding the significance of the dynamic modulus in these tests. A discrepancy is also apparent in the present tests between the stress-strain curves of fig.5, for an impact at 10m/s, where a slight increase in stiffness is apparent just prior to fracture, and those of fig.6 for two lower rates and one slightly higher rate, where this effect is not observed. Whether there is any significance in this difference in behaviour, however, is not clear.

As discussed above, the technique developed here for tensile impact testing of composite materials is either limited to specimens failing within $\sim 30 \mu\text{s}$ or requires very careful determination of the input velocity. In the longer term, therefore, it is planned to construct an extended version of the present configuration of impact tester. A second limitation relates to the testing of commercially-produced (high volume fraction) unidirectionally reinforced GFRP where, using the same design of specimen as for CFRP, it has not as yet proved possible to obtain a tensile failure in the specimen gauge region. Instead failure always occurs in shear within the specimen at the resin/fibre interface nearest to the slots in the loading bars. The use of the instrumented input bar in the extended version of the present impact tester will be required to monitor the effects of any changes in specimen design required in the solution of this problem.

CONCLUSIONS

A modified version of the SHPB apparatus has been successfully developed for the tensile impact testing of unidirectionally-reinforced CFRP. Stress equilibrium across the specimen is attained at an early stage in the test. Specimen strain is determined to an accuracy of about $\pm 3\%$ and tensile modulus to about $\pm 5\%$. Over a range from $\sim 10^{-4}$ /s to ~ 1000 /s the modulus, fracture strength and failure mode of unidirectionally-reinforced CFRP are found to be independent of strain rate.

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Fig.2 SPECIMEN DESIGN
(All dimensions in mm)

Fig.1 SCHEMATIC ARRANGEMENT AND LAGRANGE (x,t) DIAGRAM FOR MODIFIED TENSILE HOPKINSON-BAR

a) With strain gauges attached to specimen

b) With signals from gauges I and II superimposed

Fig.3 STRAIN TIME TRACES FOR IMPACT TESTS ON CFRP
(Total sweep time: 100 μ /s)

Fig. 4 HOPKINSON-BAR ANALYSIS FOR IMPACT TEST

Fig. 5 TENSILE STRESS-STRAIN CURVE FOR IMPACT AT 10m/s

Fig. 6 TENSILE STRESS-STRAIN CURVES AT THREE RATES OF STRAIN

- a) $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.0005/s$, $E = 145GPa$, $\sigma_f = 1.21 \pm 0.07GPa$ (5 tests)
- b) $\dot{\epsilon} = 7/s$, $E = 145GPa$, $\sigma_f = 1.26 \pm 0.07GPa$ (4 tests)
- c) $\dot{\epsilon} = 450/s$, $E = 149GPa$, $\sigma_f = 1.14 \pm 0.05GPa$ (4 tests)